

Distinct Parkinson's Disease Symptoms Relates To Different LFP Frequency Bands

Julia Baldi de Luccas
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-5152-
9380

Bruno Leonardo Bianqueti
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID: 000-0002-9355-084X

Arnaldo Fim Neto
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-4461-
5416

Tiago Paggi Almeida
Division of Electronic
Engineering
Aeronautics Institute of
Technology
São José dos Campos, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-5346-
6937

Takashi Yoneyama
Division of Electronic
Engineering
Aeronautics Institute of
Technology
São José dos Campos, Brazil

Maria Sheila Rocha
Neurology and Functional
Neurosurgery Division
Santa Marcelina Hospital
São Paulo, Brazil
ORCID: 000-0003-4312-3994

Diogo Coutinho Soriano
Center of Engineering,
Modeling and Applied Social
Sciences (CECS)
Federal University of ABC
São Bernardo do Campo,
Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-9804-
7477

Fabio Godinho
Functional Neurosurgery
Division
University of São Paulo
São Paulo, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-7100-
4303

Abstract— Parkinson's Disease (PD) leads to heterogeneous clinical symptoms. The underlying electrophysiological phenomena in the basal ganglia circuit remains poorly understood, imposing a major challenge for designing customized and more efficient Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) protocols to match patients' specificities and needs. To fill this gap, this work presents the correlation between clinical symptoms scores and spectral features evaluated from subthalamic nucleus (STN) local field potentials (LFP) recorded during intraoperative surgery for electrodes implantation in different PD subtypes. In addition to that, a linear regression model was designed and used to predict the symptoms scores (tremor, rigidity and bradykinesia) based on LFP rhythm's power. The findings may help to understand how the spectral STN characteristics relate to PD clinical symptoms and guide new DBS paradigms.

Keywords—Parkinson's Disease, Deep Brain Stimulation, Local Field Potentials, Linear Regression, Correlation;

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder with a significant impact in life quality, affecting about 6.1 million individuals worldwide [1]. PD symptoms are characterized by motor dysfunctions, as tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia and gait instability and also by non-motor features, such as cognitive impairment, anxiety, depression. Bradykinesia and rigidity are correlated with beta band power (13 – 35 Hz) evaluated from local field potentials (LFPs) collected from the subthalamic nucleus (STN) [3].

The dynamics properties of the beta band have emerged as an important biomarker of PD's clinical symptoms [4]. However, the correlation among the power of the obtained spectral features (integral of the power spectral density function over a bandwidth) and the symptoms' scores for the different PD subtypes – Tremor-dominant (TD) and Postural Instability and Gait Disorder (PIGD) – remain unclear, despite the valuable electrophysiological phenotypic characterization previously presented [5]. Finally, STN therapeutic stimulation

through Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) leads to differently motor improvements symptoms and it has been shown more efficient for tremor-dominant patients [6].

In the present work, we sought to investigate the correlation between the clinical scores and the spectral features for each PD subtypes. We hypothesized that the LFP power in the classical rhythms of each PD subtype (TD and PIGD) correlates differently with the clinical scores. Additionally, the predictive power of a linear regression method using different rhythms and PD subtypes was also investigated in the present work

Hence, the method herein proposed may be useful for the future feasibility of setting the STN stimulation parameters by taking into account the PD phenotype during closed-looped control with impact on elaboration of the adaptive DBS (aDBS) equipment, an emergent DBS method for reducing costs as well as further improving the PD treatment [7][8].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Patients and Data Acquisition

All PD patients were recruited from the Movement Disorders Outpatient Clinic of Santa Marcelina Hospital (São Paulo, SP, Brazil). They were classified into clinical PD subtypes after Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS) evaluation. Twenty-five PD patients were subtyped as TD (N=11), PIGD (N=13) and undetermined (N=1). Subsequently, the cohort underwent DBS electrodes placement, in which a total of 14 patients were operated bilaterally (5 TD, 8 PIGD and 1 undetermined). Among all patients, there were 2 cases in which no LFP were recorded (1 TD and 1 PIGD), totalizing 37 LFP signals acquired (15 TD, 20 PIGD and 2 undetermined). All patients provided prior written consent in agreement to Santa Marcelina Hospital Ethics Committee (CAAE: 62418316.9.2004.0066).

LFP recordings were acquired during 60s from the dorsolateral portion of each STN hemisphere by using macroelectrodes of 1 mm diameter and 1 k Ω impedance (FHC

– Greenville – USA) attached to LeadPoint register system (Medtronic – Minneapolis – USA), sampled at 24 kHz, and online bandpass filtered (5 Hz to 5 kHz). All patients were awake during the procedure, at rest condition, and after twelve hours of dopaminergic medication washout.

B. Offline Signal processing

During offline processing in Matlab 2015a, all LFP signals were notch filtered at 60 Hz and harmonics, downsampled to 1 kHz (decimation method), band-pass filtered (2-400 Hz) by 6th order IIR Butterworth and z-score normalized. Power spectrum density (PSD) was estimated by the Welch method by using Hamming windows of 4 s and 50% overlap [9][10]. The power was estimated by means of the area under PSD curve for a range of frequency bands defined as: theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8 – 13 Hz), beta 1 (13 – 22 Hz), beta 2 (22 - 35 Hz), gamma 1 (35 - 100 Hz), gamma 2 (100 – 150 Hz) and gamma 3 (150 - 200 Hz).

C. Correlation analysis

Normality for all data was checked by D'Agostino & Pearson omnibus normality test. The correlation between LFP power and UPDRS clinical scores of tremor, rigidity and bradykinesia symptoms for both TD and PIGD patients was estimated through Pearson's coefficient (r) for normal distributions and Spearman's coefficient for non-normal distributions. Significant correlation was determined based on a t-distribution with $(n-2)$ degrees of freedom. Statistical significance was considered for $p < 0.05$ [11].

D. Linear Regression Analysis

Linear fitting regression was obtained between clinical scores of each symptom (i.e. tremor, rigidity and bradykinesia) and LFP power considering subtypes separately [11][12]. The R^2 value was quantified to obtain the goodness of fit.

Furthermore, prediction tests of the same symptoms clinical scores based on LFP power were performed using linear regression with k -fold cross-validation ($k = 10$). The procedure was carried out distinguishing the subtypes and repeated 20 times in order to reach greater statistical reliability [11][12]. The mean quadratic error and the standard deviation were computed for all tests.

The tests were performed again using shuffled clinical scores among LFP records in order to analyze the prediction performance, simulating a random regression condition. The quadratic errors from the original and scrambled data were checked to normal distribution using D'Agostino & Pearson omnibus normality test and then compared with paired Student's t-test for normal distributions Wilcoxon for non-normal distributions. Statistically significant differences were considered for $p < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

No significant correlation was found between tremor score and LFP power in the classical rhythms for TD subtype. For PIGD patients, it was found significant correlation for beta 2 band. When analyzed rigidity for PIGD patients, there was an inverse correlation for the alpha band in contrast to beta 2, the latter disclosed a positive correlation. For TD patients, rigidity was found to be poorly correlated. Regarding bradykinesia, no significant correlation was

observed for TD subtype and positive correlation was found in gamma 1 for PIGD subtype.

Fig 1: correlation between LFP rhythms' power and clinical scores for tremor (A), rigidity (B) and bradykinesia (C) for TD (blue) and PIGD (red) patients. Dashed lines indicate threshold significance for each subtype.

Best fit quality was achieved for TD patients in gamma 3, gamma 1 and beta 1 for, respectively, tremor, rigidity and bradykinesia clinical scores. On the other hand, for PIGD patients, best fit occurred for the gamma 1, beta 2 and gamma 1 bands for the aforementioned clinical scores. These results are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Best linear fittings for PD symptoms.

	Tremor		Rigidity		Bradykinesia	
	Band	R^2	Band	R^2	Band	R^2
TD	γ_3	0.129	γ_1	0.183	β_1	0.078
PIGD	γ_1	0.119	β_2	0.356	γ_1	0.149

Concerning the prediction test for TD subtype (Fig. 2A), results revealed a poor performance in all frequency bands for predicting tremor. For rigidity, good performance occurred for beta 2 ($p < 0.0001$), gamma 2 ($p < 0.0001$) and gamma 3 ($p = 0.0121$). Considering bradykinesia, the prediction test showed poor performance for all frequency bands.

Considering PIGD subtype analysis (Fig. 2B), regression analysis provided lower quadratic errors than the random regressor for tremor based on alpha ($p < 0.0001$) and gamma 3 ($p = 0.0003$). For rigidity, it was computed excellent performance for alpha and beta 2 bands ($p < 0.0001$ for both bands). Finally, gamma 1 ($p < 0.0001$) has achieved improved performance and suggest to be a possible good predictor for bradykinesia.

Fig. 2: Mean quadratic error and standard deviation obtained from prediction test using linear regression with original (orange) and shuffled (grey) data for TD (A) and PIGD (B) subtype.

IV. DISCUSSION

Correlation between PD symptoms with LFP power have been covered in the literature, specially within frequency range between 8-35 Hz, also referred to as beta band for some authors, being demonstrated that the degree of suppression of oscillations in this interval positively correlates with improvement of motor symptoms after dopamine intake. These findings, however, refer only to rigidity and bradykinesia, with no correlation found correlation for tremor [3]. This behavior is not only observed in response to drug administration, but also with STN stimulation, which improvement for rigidity and bradykinesia can be predicted based on LFP beta power [13].

Our results partially corroborate with these previous findings, even considering different parameters for analysis. Regarding tremor, it demonstrated no significant correlation

at any frequency bands for TD subtype and positive correlation at beta 2 for PIGD subtype. Concerning to the relationship between rigidity and beta band (8-35 Hz range), we found significant correlation. However, our results indicate that possibly exists a difference between how PD subtypes are affected by such oscillatory patterns. PIGD subtype individuals have akinesia/rigidity predominantly, instead of TD patients, that have tremor as a prominent symptom [14]. Based on this, it is coherent that PIGD patients have stronger correlation with rigidity than TD, that shows no significant correlation for this symptom for all considered bands. Moreover, by dividing this frequency interval into three bands, it's possible to perceive that are different demeanors between alpha, beta 1 and beta 2 for PIGD subtype. Alpha band discloses inverse correlation with rigidity, whereas beta 1 shows no correlation, and beta 2 a positive correlation. In other study, alpha (8-13 Hz) and beta (13-30 Hz) have also shown distinct correlation, in which alpha shown to be positively correlated, while beta discloses inverse behavior. However, this analysis considered contralateral summed hemi body UPDRS score, instead of rigidity score individually [13]. Regarding bradykinesia, even though this symptom appears to correlate with beta band [3][13], our data did not reflect this finding.

Furthermore, the results about correlation are in agreement with the ones obtained from linear regression prediction. As it can be seen, frequency bands that demonstrated to be strongly correlated with rigidity for PIGD subtype showed off as a good feature for predicting it clinical score. This also corroborates with the fact that the best fitting for rigidity considering PIGD patients occurred at beta 2. Although tremor had shown significant correlation for PIGD subtype at beta 2, alpha and gamma 3 bands demonstrated to be good predictors of this symptom. For bradykinesia, gamma 1 has shown to be a good predictor, being the one with the best fitting for PIGD subtype and also having significant correlation for this symptom.

The positive relationship between gamma 1 and bradykinesia is interesting and requires further attention, since gamma oscillations are known to be prokinetic [15]. Gamma band increased synchronization occurs after treatment with levodopa, when bradykinesia is ameliorated, and before voluntary movements [16]. Given that, it was reasonable to expect an inverse correlation between gamma and bradykinesia.

V. CONCLUSION

The results here obtained suggest that different PD symptoms are associated with various LFP frequency bands, which depends on each PD clinical subtype. These findings corroborate with the need for customized DBS protocols based on the patient's main clinical characteristics for matching electrophysiological induced changes aiming a more efficient treatment.

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REFERENCES

- [1] GBD 2016 Parkinson's Disease Collaborators. Global, regional, and national burden of Parkinson's disease, 1990–2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *The Lancet Neurology*, v. 17, n. 11, p. 939-953, 2018.
- [2] M. R. DeLong, T. Wichmann. Circuits and circuit disorders of the basal ganglia. *Archives of neurology*, v. 64, n. 1, p. 20-24, 2007.
- [3] A. Kühn, A. Kupsch, G. H. Schneider, & P. Brown. Reduction in subthalamic 8–35 Hz oscillatory activity correlates with clinical improvement in Parkinson's disease. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, v. 23, n. 7, p. 1956-1960, 2006.
- [4] C. Hammond, H. Bergman, P. Brown. Pathological synchronization in Parkinson's disease: networks, models and treatments. *Trends in neurosciences*, v. 30, n. 7, p. 357-364, 2007.
- [5] I. Telkes et al. Local field potentials of subthalamic nucleus contain electrophysiological footprints of motor subtypes of Parkinson's disease. *Proceedings Of The National Academy Of Sciences*, [s.l.], v. 115, n. 36, p.1-10, 21 ago. 2018.
- [6] Katz, M., Luciano, M. S., Carlson, K., Luo, P., Marks Jr, W. J., Larson, P. S., ... & Reda, D. J. (2015). Differential effects of deep brain stimulation target on motor subtypes in Parkinson's disease. *Annals of neurology*, 77(4), 710-719.
- [7] S. Little et al. Adaptive deep brain stimulation in advanced Parkinson disease. *Annals Of Neurology*, [s.l.], v. 74, n. 3, p.449-457, 12 jul. 2013.
- [8] A. Priori, G. Foffani, L. Rossi, S. Marceglia. Adaptive deep brain stimulation (aDBS) controlled by local field potential oscillations. *Experimental neurology*, v. 245, p. 77-86, 2013.
- [9] P Welch. The use of fast Fourier transform for the estimation of power spectra: a method based on time averaging over short, modified periodograms. *IEEE Transactions on audio and electroacoustics*, v. 15, n. 2, p. 70-73, 1967.
- [10] J. L Semmlow. *Biosignal and medical image processing*. CRC press, 2008.
- [11] R. E. Walpole, R. H. Myers, S. L. Myers, & K. Ye. *Probability and statistics for engineers and scientists (Vol. 5)*. New York: Macmillan. 1993.
- [12] S. Theodoridis, A. Pikrakis, K. Koutroumbas, & D Cavouras. *Introduction to pattern recognition: a matlab approach*. Academic Press. 2010.
- [13] N. J. Ray; N. Jenkinson; S. Wang; P. Holland; J. S. Brittain; C. Joint; J. F. Stein; T Aziz. Local field potential beta activity in the subthalamic nucleus of patients with Parkinson's disease is associated with improvements in bradykinesia after dopamine and deep brain stimulation. *Experimental neurology*, v. 213, n. 1, p. 108-113, 2008.
- [14] A. Zaidel., D. Arkadir, Z. Israel, and H. Bergman. Akineto-rigid vs. tremor syndromes in Parkinsonism. *Curr. Opin. Neurol.* 22, 387–393, 2009.
- [15] P. Brown. Oscillatory nature of human basal ganglia activity: relationship to the pathophysiology of Parkinson's disease. *Movement disorders: official journal of the Movement Disorder Society*, v. 18, n. 4, p. 357-363, 2003.
- [16] M. Cassidy, P. Mazzone, A. Oliviero, A. Insola, P. Tonali, V. Di Lazzaro, P. Brown. Movement-related changes in synchronisation in the human basal ganglia. *Brain*, 125:1235–1246, 2002.